

Feathered Serpent's cult

By Bertrand Lobjois, Université Paris I - Sorbonne

Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesoamerican Religions, Aztec Religions, Mayan Religions, Teotihuacan Religions, Toltec Religion, Mexican Religion, Mexica, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Language, Uto-Aztecan, Cholula Religion, Xochicalco Religion, Cacaxtla Religion

The choice of the name "Feathered Serpent" is due to the fact that there are translations for most of the Indigenous peoples who have lived in present-day Mexico and the United States of America. While the Nahuatl name "Quetzalcoatl" is probably the most well-known by most readers, it is a Late Postclassic and colonial Nahuatl term used mostly in the Highlands of Mexico. In fact, the names "Kukulkan" in Maya Tzeltal, "Q'uc'umatz" in Q'iche' are local versions of the Feathered Serpent. This onomastic diversity is accompanied by epithets that denote positive and negative attributes, powers, and domains. Speaking of the positive ones, he's considered as creator of humanity, provider of fire and food, patron of artists, announcer of rains, organizer of time and stars, young conquering warrior, priest concerned with rules, etc. About the negative ones, he is the first to sacrifice the gods, claims for human sacrifices. It then becomes Naxcit, Hun Ac El, Kan Tepeu, Nanahuatl, Ce Acatl, Ehécatl, etc. Its own name is the perfect of complementary opposites: the quetzal feathers remind us its heavenly nature, and the coatl or serpent refers to its chthonian aspect. Despite the cultural, linguistic, and figurative diversity inherent in the Mesoamerican religious Tradition, this entry highlights shared aspects of the Feathered Serpent cult in ancient Mesoamerica, taking into account colonial texts written in Spanish or Nahuatl, pre-Hispanic depictions, and some ethnographic testimonies.

Date Range: 100 CE - 1521 CE

Region: Mesoamerica

Region tags: Mesoamerica (general), Mesoamerica, Mexico

General view of the theoretical cultural superarea between Late Preclassic and Late Postclassic.

参与者的状态

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

来源

理解这一问题的书面资料：

- Source 1: Editorial Raíces. La serpiente emplumada. *Arqueología mexicana* 52. Editorial Raíces, 2002.
- Source 2: Florescano, Enrique. *Quetzalcóatl y los mitos fundadores de Mesoamérica*. Mexico City, Taurus, 2004.
- Source 3: Sugiyama, Saburo. Teotihuacan as an Origin for Postclassic Feathered Serpent Symbolism. In Carrasco, David, Lindsay Jones & Scott Sessions. *Mesoamerica's Classic Heritage*, pp. 145-164, Boulder, University Press of Colorado, 2002.
- Source 1: Berrin, Kathleen (ed.). *Feathered Serpents and Floering Trees*, The Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco, San Francisco, 1988.

- Source 2: Brittenham, Claudia. *The Murals of Cacaxtla: The Power of Painting in Ancient Central Mexico*, University of Texas Press, 2015
- Source 3: Carrasco, David. *Quetzalcoatl and the Irony of Empire: Myths and Prophecies in the Aztec Tradition*, University of Chicago Press, 1992
- Source 1: Dupey-García, Élodie. Serpent emplumé et serpent peint. Le vent et l'arc-en-ciel dans la culture nahuatl préhispanique. In Arnaud Dubois, Jean-Baptiste Eczet, Adeline Grand-Clément & Charlotte Ribeyrol, *Arcs-en-ciel et couleurs*, pp.11-148, CNRS Éditions, Paris, 2018.
- Source 2: Dupey-García, Élodie. Quetzalcoatl in Nahua Myths and Rituals. Inconspicuous or Omnipresent Protagonist?, in Élodie Dupey-García & Elena Mazzetto (eds.), *Mesoamerican Rituals and the Solar Cycle. New Perspectives on the Veintena Festivals*, pp.79-100, Peter Lang Publishing, 2021
- Source 3: Espinosa Pineda, Gabriela, La fauna de Ehécatl, in Yolotl González Torres (ed.), *Animales y plantas en la cosmovisión mesoamericana*, pp. 255-304, Plaza y Valdés Editores, Mexico City, 2001
- Source 1: García Barrios, Ana, Dragones del diluvio en Mesoamérica. La serpiente emplumada de Teotihuacan y el cocodrilo venado estelar maya, in Itzel Rodríguez González (ed.), *Animalística: XXXVIII Coloquio Internacional de Historia del Arte*, pp. 79-130, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico City, 2023
- Source 2: López Austin, Alfredo, Quetzalcoatl dédoublé: religion mésoaméricaine et céramique mixtèque, in Aline Hémond & Pierre Ragon (eds.), *L'image au Mexique: usages, appropriations et transgressions*, pp. 15-34, L'Harmattan, Paris, 2001.
- Source 1: López Austin, Alfredo, and Leonardo López Luján. Mito y realidad de zuyuá : serpiente emplumada y las transformaciones mesoamericanas del clásico al posclásico, Fondo de Cultura Económica, 2021
- Source 2: Kowalski, Jeff Karl, and Cinthya Kristen Graham. *Twin Tollans : Chichén Itzá, Tula, and the epiclassic to early postclassic Mesoamerican world*. Washington, D.C. Dumbarton Oaks Research Library & Collection, 2007.
- Source 3: Nicholson, Henry B. *Topiltzin Quetzalcoatl: The Once and Future Lord of the Toltecs*, University Press of Colorado, Boulder, 2001

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

理解这一问题的在线资料:

- Source 1 URL: <http://cdigital.uv.mx/handle/123456789/1232>
- Source 1 Description: Morante López, Rubén, *El Templo de las Serpientes Emplumadas de Xochicalco, La palabra y el hombre*, 91, pp. 113-133, 1994
- Source 2 URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S095653611900035X/type/journal_article
- Source 2 Description: Price, T. Douglas, Michael W. Spence & Fred Longstaffe, *The Temple of Quetzalcoatl, Teotihuacan: New Data on the Origins of Sacrificial Victims*, *Ancient Mesoamerica*, (32)2, pp. 215-230
- Source 3 URL: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0956536100001954/type/journal_article
- Source 3 Description: Ringle, William, Tomás Gallareta Negrón & George J. Bey, *The Return of Quetzalcoatl: Evidence for the spread of a world religion during the Epiclassic period*, *Ancient Mesoamerica*, (9)2, pp. 183-232.

- Source 1 URL: <https://historicas.unam.mx/publicaciones/publicadigital/libros/hombre/dios.html>
- Source 1 Description: López Austin, Alfredo. *Hombre dios Religión y política en el mundo náhuatl*. Ciudad de México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2015.
- Source 2 URL: <https://sup-infor.com/etudes/etudes.htm>
- Source 2 Description: Graulich, Michel. *Quetzalcoatl y el espejismo de Tollan*. Sup-infor, 2003.
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.mesoweb.com/es/articulos/sub/Tepanec-Quetzalcoatl.pdf>
- Source 3 Description: López Luján, Leonardo, *Tepanec Quetzalcóatl (Feathered Serpent) and Tlaltecuhli, Goddess of the Earth*, in Cécile Ganteaume (ed.), *Infinity of Nations: Art and History in the Collections of the National Museum of the American Indian, Smithsonian National Museum of the American Indian, Washington D.C.*

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

- Source 1 URL: <https://florentinecodex.getty.edu>
- Source 1 Description: Richter, K. & Houtrouw, M. (2023). *Digital Florentine Codex*. Getty Research Institute
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.iiia.unam.mx/publicacion/relaciones-geograficas-del-siglo-xvi-tlaxcala>
- Source 2 Description: Rojas, Gabriel de. *Relación de Cholula*, in René Acuña (ed.). *Relaciones geográficas del siglo XVI: Tlaxcala. tomo segundo*, Ciudad de México, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2017.
- Source 3 URL: <https://historicas.unam.mx/publicaciones/catalogo/ficha?id=735pdf>
- Source 3 Description: Alvarado Tezozomoc, Hernando. *Crónica mexicana Manuscrito Kraus 117*, Ciudad de México, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Instituto de Investigaciones Históricas, 2021.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

– Yes

Notes: The use of Nahuatl language could be a criterion to be part of the community, at least in Postclassic Central Mexico.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 与生俱来（成员身份在这种社会是默认的）：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 基于个人选择：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由社会阶层赋予：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由特定年龄阶段赋予：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由性别赋予：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由参与特定仪式赋予：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由其它因素而赋予：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：

– Yes

Notes: Priests may have been retributed for their performances, but most of them were actually political rulers, as the Feathered Serpent is represented and described as a priest and a ruler.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：

– Yes

Notes: The intervention of political regime in the construction of religious consists in obliging macehualtin (commoners) to fulfill with their tequitl (duty as it could be translated in english). It means that macehualtin were used as working force. Artists (toltecah) were feeded and payed by the tlahtoani to design and prepare the ornaments and wall painting of the building. Some of them were directly hosted in the totocalli, an exclusive space in the tlahtoani. Most of them were grouped by techniques. In case of important work, artists and sculptors could be recruited among surrounding cities around in Mexico valley.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：

– Yes

Notes: According to different nahua myths, Quetzalcoatl was the main priest and ruler of Tollan, and imposed strict life and ritualistic rules to his subjects and to himself strictly. As a matter of fact, he decided to exile himself after being drunk and having a sex intercourse.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税)：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口，数字)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量(在样本区域人口中的百分比，数字)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体性质【请选其一】：

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

在该宗教团体中是否存在被认可的领导者：

– Yes

Notes: Quetzalcoatl was also a title for two priest-leaders among the Mexicas in Late Postclassic. Dual power seems to have been practiced at Epiclassic Tlaxcala site Cacaxtla: wall paintings of Building A represent two individuals respectively dressed in jaguar and eagles features. A Feathered Serpent follows the eagle-dressed. To Graulich, this very particular painting has solar aspects, proper to a ruler. Things are not so clear in other Mesoamerican cultures. In Teotihuacan, Mexican archaeologist suggested that the Feathered Serpent was one of the four lineages that shared and co-ruled this metropolis. López Austin and Luján consider that the Feathered Serpent was the base of the Zuyuan ideological and political system .

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Prehispanic codices from the Mixteca, the Maya region and of Mexico Highlands are good examples of them. Most of them were destroyed during the forced evangelization.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Actually, most of them were orally transmitted.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

– Yes

Notes: In Postclassic myths, the Feathered Serpent is described as ruler of the toltecah, which can be boldly translated as “artist”. Quetzalcoatl is presented as the first artist, the first who draws, sculpts, molds, inspiring toltecah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来源于凡人：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这一经典是否可以改变：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：

– Yes

Notes: At least, colonial accounts like Sahagun explains that noble children and future priests were taught to read tonalamatl. Let's remind that the calmecac's patron god was Quetzalcoatl and its main priest has the title of Quetzalcoatl.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 可以抛开这些机构来诠释经典吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 只有被正式批准的人员才可以诠释经典：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：

– Yes

Notes: These individuals taught the scripture and reading of códices at the calmecac, where elite children received their education.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 在一般的定居地，所有宗教纪念性质建筑、纪念物面积所占百分比是多少：

– Field doesn't know

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的面积，以平方米计

– I don't know

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的高度，以米计

– I don't know

↳ 一般纪念物、建筑的尺寸，平方米

– Field doesn't know

↳ 一般纪念建筑、纪念物的高度，米

– Field doesn't know

↳ 在最大的定居地，所有宗教纪念物、纪念建筑总体面积所占区域百分比是多少？

– Field doesn't know

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 陵墓

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

公墓

– Yes

Notes: Common people were buried in the ground of their own house.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

庙宇

– Yes

Notes: There is an interesting variety of temples dedicated to the Feathered Serpent. In Early Classic Teotihuacan, the pyramid had a squared-design, as well as in Epiclassic Xochicalco and Early Postclassic Chichen Itza, Tula, and Mayapan. In Late Postclassic Mexico Valley, Quetzalcoatl temples combined a rectangular shape structure topped by a half-circular building as it can be observed in Calixtlahuaca, Tlatelolco and Tenochtitlan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

圣坛

– Yes

Notes: In Chichen Itza, anthropomorphic and zoomorphic altars were disposed in front of the main entrance of the Kukulcan Pyramid and the Temple of the Warriors Pyramid. Similar altars were settled in Tula. They were called with an inappropriate maya term, chac mool, by French explorer Désiré Charnay. In the National Museum of Anthropology, the visitor can see a Mexica cylindrical altar with the reliefs of two feathered serpents facing each other.

用于礼拜的标志性建筑

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

大规模集会点（庭院、广场等，用可见物或结构永久划分出来的场所）

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

其它种类的宗教纪念性建筑物

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

是否存在表征标志

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

– Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 眼睛（是否写实）

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然的存在(兽形)

– Yes

Notes: As his name said, the Feathered serpent is a mash-up of (rattle) snake with its body covered with long green feathers of the precious bird, the quetzal. So the Feathered Serpent may appear behind or besides a human being. A first example might be the Acuecuexatl stone. Sculpted in low-relief for the inauguration of an aqueduct during Mexica tlahtoani Axayacatl's reign. Axacayatl is represented with an undulating quetzalcoatl besides him. A former example is the sculpted relief of Ce Acatl Topiltzin Quetzalcoatl on the bedrock of Cerro La Malinche, very close to the core of the archaeological site of Tula, Hidalgo. While Ce Acatl is bleeding his left ear with a spine, a feathered serpent undulates right behind him. A very similar iconography can be seen at Chichen Itza's Lower and Upper Temple of the Jaguars.

↳ 超自然的存在(地貌外形)

– Yes

Notes: In Late Postclassic Mexico Valley, several Quetzalcoatl sculptures have the belower side sculpted with a relief of Tlaltecuhтли, lord/lady of the Earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然的存在(人形)

– Yes

Notes: The main anthropomorphic representation of the Feathered Serpent is known as 9 Wind, who is largely represented and mentioned in Mixteca códices and Colonial chronicles. The best description of 9 Wind is proposed by Diego Durán in his Book of Rites and Gods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然的存在(抽象的象征符号)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 对来世的描绘

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 教义方面 (比如, 十字架、三位一体、密特拉教符号)

– Yes

Notes: For example, the shell jewel pectoral is a common feature that reminds the Feathered Serpent relation with wind, fertility, and pregnancy. It appears on the reliefs of the Feathered Serpent pyramids of Teotihuacan or Xochicalco. Flint knives can be figured instead of the shells, reminder the role of the Feathered Serpent with the sacrifice of the gods, then with human beings. Cross shapes can sometimes appear on feathered serpent jaws: at Chichen Itza, Feathered Serpent heads at the bottom of the plumed columns contains these crosses, symbols of fire or the planet Venus.

↳ 人类

– Yes

Notes: The human characteristics change according to the region and culture. However, the Feathered Serpent may be pictured as an ixiptla. This last nahua concepts means that a human person can personify the god by wearing his particular features, such as his bird-mask called ehecaxayactl, his wind shell pectoral called ehecacozcatl, his incense purse called copalxiquipilli, &c.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 表征有其它特色：

– Yes

Notes: Spranz listed the Feathered Serpent as Ehecatl in the Borgia codex group. However, the list can

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

– Yes

Notes: In the case of the Feathered Serpent, Cholula (Puebla State) was the main pilgrimage during the Late Postclassic. Mesoamerican rulers were obliged to present themselves before Quetzalcoatl's image so that they can confirm their ruler's status and paraphernalia. But some cities like Xochicalco, Chichen Itza, Tula, Calixtlahuaca did have dedicated temples to Quetzalcoatl. In Tenochtitlan or Tlatelolco recinct, several buildings were directly related with Quetzalcoatl.

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：

“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Classic Teotihuacan, religious buildings were built to reproduce the surrounding mountains around the site. The temple of the Feathered Serpents had its main stair oriented to the West. The mains temples of Quetzalcoatl in Tenochtitlan and Tlatelolco sacred precincts had their entrance oriented to the east.

有朝圣活动吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 朝圣活动如何严格：

– Obligatory for some

Notes: According to Colonial accounts, the Cholula pilgrimage was obligatory for the Mesoamerican rulers, so they could receive their ruling artifacts and confirm their political and religious power.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

– Yes

Notes: Nahuatl religious tradition consider three animistic centers in the human body: teyolía, tonalli y ihiyotl are respectively located on the top of the head, in the heart and in the liver of each human body, according to López Austin (1980). According to Velázquez García (2023), some Maya texts mention the existence of a dualistic nature of human beings, but not in the same way that Postclassic nahuats did.

↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质

– Yes

Notes: As explained by Velázquez García (2023), animistic entities do possess consciousness and several levels of autosufficiency, while animistic forces aren't related with intellectual abilities. These forces flow in the entire body, but it mainly lays in the chest, more precisely in the heart. In Nahuatl Postclassic thought, there were three main animistic centers in the human body: the head, the heart and the liver. López Austin explained that each center was the recipient of a different energy: the tonalli, the teyolía y the ihiyotl, following the three human body parts already mentioned. According to the Florentine Codex, the newborn tonalli could be injured, so Quetzalcoatl was prayed and tobacco was burnt to prevent this affection.

↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为是非物质的，在本体论上不同于身体

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

对来世的信仰：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

在这个世界上的转世

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 火化

– Yes

Notes: In Nahua Postclassic tradition, pipiltin (noble men) were incinerated as the Feathered Serpent threw himself in the fire, so he can be reborn as the Morning Star or the Sun.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制成木乃伊

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 埋葬：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 遗体被蜷屈 (腿部弯曲或身体蜷缩)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 遗体被伸展(或躺或卧)

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 遗体竖立 (遗体以站姿安葬)：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 遗体以其他方式安葬：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

是否存在陪葬品：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

有正式的葬礼吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 有一个至上之神存在

– Yes

Notes: The supreme God of the Nahua tradition is called Ometeotl, which means God Two, with a male part and a female part. According to Florentine Codex, Quetzalcoatl was one of their four sons.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神是人形：

– Yes

Notes: In Nahua religion, Ometeotl, or God Two, is depicted in Colonial codices with anthropomorphic features.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神是天神

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme Gods in Nahua religion live on the upper level of the heavens. In the case of the Feathered Serpent, he lives with the other gods, on a lower level of the heavens. When it is represented as a feathered serpent in sculpted reliefs (as in Chichen Itza, Tula and Tenochtitlan), it could represent skybands that guides the Sun from dawn to sunset. In Cacaxtla's B Building, the Feathered Serpent is painted behind an eagle-warrior. In Mesoamerican thought, the eagle symbolizes the Sun.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神是地府的神灵（地底世界的）：

– No

Notes: The Feathered Serpent isn't an underworld deity, but it is also related with the kingdom of death, Mictlan in Nahua traditions and myths. It is said that Quetzalcoatl stole the bones of a former humanity to bring them back to the surface of the earth, and create another humanity. However, the main god of the Underworld, Mictlantecuhtli, tried to impeach Quetzalcoatl's return to the surface of the world by sending quails. The birds surprised Quetzalcoatl on his way back, obliging him to drop the bones and splitting them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神与君主不分（王=至高的神）

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 君主被视作至上之神的表现和化身：

– No

Notes: In the Postclassic Mesoamerican myth, the Feathered Serpent is described as a ruler presented as Tollan or Zuyua. He is indeed presented as the archetype of the priest-ruler-warrior.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神和精英阶层有亲属关系

– Yes

Notes: In the Mexica rulers lineage, the Toltec figure of Quetzalcoatl is presented as a direct ancestor.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神和精英有其它类型的效忠关系

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至高之神是不可质疑的善

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to Nahuatl and Spanish accounts for Late Postclassic and Colonial times in Central Mexico Highlands, Quetzalcoatl is presented as the creator of the humanity, the flowers, and the plants that feed him, the arts, &c. However, the Feathered Serpent also claims for sacrifices, offerings. He should be rewarded and thanked for the services rendered to humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神的其他特征：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神具有关于这个世界的知识：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制：

– Yes

Notes: According to Colonial chronicles like Sahagún or Leyenda de los Soles, the Feathered Serpent is directly related to human conception, arts, agriculture, and even with war.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，至上之神都可以看到你

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

– Yes

Notes: As creator of time and calendar, the Feathered Serpent is deeply related with the reading and interpretation of the tonalpohualli (count of the days) in the Postclassic Nahua tradition. This count of the days helps to understand the personality of each human being, according to his/her birthday.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇/你将来会做什么（预测的能力）：

– Yes

Notes: As creator of time and calendar, The Feathered Serpent is deeply related with the reading and interpretation of the tonalpohualli in the Nahua tradition. This book of counts helps to understand the personality of each human being, according to his/her birthday.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神能奖赏

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神能惩罚：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神对这个世界上可以施发间接的因果效力：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神展现其积极的情感：

– Yes

Notes: The Feathered Serpent is summoned by Nahua grand-parents before and after the birth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神展现其负面的情感：

– Yes

Notes: Jacinto de la Serna's about Quetzalcoatl killing his uncles is quite interesting: as they tried to kill him and his father Mixcoatl, Quetzalcoatl decided to kill them to protect him.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神有饥饿感：

– Yes

Notes: In Nahua myths of the creation of the Sun and the Moon, the Feathered Serpent deserves the sacrifice and offerings that human beings can prepare and act. It is a way to retribute the sacrifice the gods made with their own life to create the Sun and the Moon and make them move later.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 除了至高之神以外，允许崇拜其他超自然存在吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神具备/展现出其他一些特征：

– Yes [specify]: As an anthropomorphic god, Quetzalcoatl is also known by his birthday, Ce Acatl (One Reed), or as the Wind God (Ehécatl). His attributes like the wind shield, the wind jewel, the jaguar skin conic hat, the wind mask were widely shared during the Postclassic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 至上之神和生灵有沟通：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：

– Yes

Notes: About this very category of non-human supernatural beings, Nahua and Maya

cosmovision considers the existence of a zoomorphic double for each human being. In The Leyenda de los Soles, Quetzalcoatl revives after being killed and having dropped the bones of the former humanity. As he saw the bones picked and destroyed by quails, Quetzalcóatl asks directly to his nahualli what he would do know after this incident that compromises. Even if the text doesn't explain what the appearance of the nahualli, scholars considered that it was a feathered serpent. However Quetzalcoatl had other nahuallime, like the ant or the opossum.

↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于特定的领域人类事务 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域 :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区内无所不知 :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区以外无所不知：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，非人类的超自然存都可以看到你：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 不论你置身何处非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你将来的人生际遇／你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有其他的认知：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在可以奖赏：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在可以惩罚：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：

– Yes [specify]: Mesoamerican religious tradition considers the existence of several animistic entities called nahualli (as an animal double for Nahua tradition), ways in the Maya tradition. These entities could be injured or even killed by ritual specialists (Martínez González, 2011).

↳ 有半人半神的存在：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

– Yes

Notes: Nahualli are mainly zoomorphic. As any human being is considered having a nahualli, it can be manipulated to attack other nahuallime and human being animistic center.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 万神庙的其他组织方式：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

– Yes

Notes: The cause can be investigated, but not certainly known.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 只由至上之神完成

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

– Yes

Notes: One can't be punished by non-human supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

– Field doesn't know

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

存在某种末世论吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 末世就在今生：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 末世在未来确定的时间点出现：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 末世出现在在不久的将来，但是时间不确定：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 末世出现在在遥远的将来，时间不确定：

– Yes

Notes: Here we can remind the role of the Feathered Serpent during the creation and destruction of different eras, called suns in the Late Postclassic Mexico Highlands (Leyenda de los Soles, Histoyre du Méchique, Florentine Codex)

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 末世在其他时间出现：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 信徒需要完成特殊的任务才能使得末世来临：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 神圣审判的活动：

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 世界的重建：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 开始一个新的时间周期：

– Yes

Notes: Here we can remind the role of the Feathered Serpent during the creation and destruction of different eras, called suns in the Late Postclassic Mexico Highlands (Leyenda de los Soles, Histoyre du Méchique, Florentine Codex)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 建立一个新的政治体系：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 建立一个新的宗教体系：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 会有人在末世幸存吗：

– No

Notes: They is a new humanity created by the gods.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

这种区别的性质是什么：

– Strongly present and highlighted

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的观念模糊有不明显的联系：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的实体有明显的联系：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

专门的道德规范和客观的宇宙秩序的有联系（比如业力）：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

专门的道德规范以某种方式和人形的存在相联系：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

专门的道德规范和人形化的存在的命令有明显的联系：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 专门的道德规范和形而上的没有特别联系：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 道德规范适用于：

– All individuals within society

Notes: Nahua rulers, nobles, and priests are supposed to respect these rules. As an example, in Nahua myths, Quetzalcoatl is presented as the supreme priest-ruler. After being tricked by Tezcatlipoca or one of his avatars, Quetzalcoatl gets drunk and sleeps with his sister. The day after, he realized how he infringed his own rules, so he decides to leave Tollan, the capital of his realm and find his way and death to a place called Tlillan Tlapallan, "The Place of Black and Red".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 诚实/忠信/正直：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 勇敢（在战斗中）：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 勇敢（一般意义上）：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 同情心／善解人意／善良／仁爱：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 仁慈／宽宥／包容：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 慷慨／博施济众：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 无私／无私奉献：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 仗义／正气：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 仪式纯洁／奉守礼制／戒绝不纯洁之源：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 对人尊敬／讲礼貌：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 家庭内的恭顺／孝顺：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 忠实/忠诚 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 合作 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 独立/创造性/自由 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 节制/节俭 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 忍耐力/刚毅/耐心 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 勤奋/自律/卓越 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 果敢/果断/自信/主动 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 强壮（身体的）：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 权力/地位/高贵：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 谦卑/谦虚：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 满足/恬静/平和：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 愉悦/激情/开心：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 乐观/希望：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 感恩/答谢：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 尊敬/敬畏/赞叹 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 信仰/信念/信任/信奉 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 智慧/理解力 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 洞察力/聪颖 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 美丽/魅力 :

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ (身体的) 干净/整齐 :

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 宗教团体宣扬其他的重要美德 :

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 一夫一妻制 (男性)：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 一夫一妻制 (女性)：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (男性)：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (女性)：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

— Yes

Notes: In the Florentine Codex, Quetzalcoatl, as the priest and ruler of Tullan, often fasts. The ritual of fasting was fundamental in Nahua priests and rulers life, specially during the veintenas festivals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物（对想吃的食物的禁忌）吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

— Yes

Notes: Colonial accounts, Prehispanic codex and Mesoamerican iconographies often show rulers and nobles bleeding their ears, nose, tongues, and legs son they can offer it to the gods.

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

— Yes

Notes: The self-sacrifice rituals mentioned above are an example of this.

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— Yes

Notes: Durán explains the entire process of selection of the slave who would represent Quetzalcoatl during his feast in Cholula. The merchants were used to buy him at the slave market of Azcapotzalco.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— Yes

Notes: Children were sacrificed by Quetzalcoatl priests in Cholula, in order to win the battle against the Spaniards and their allies. In archaeological context, sacrificed children were buried in Quetzalcoatl Temple R in the Sacred Precinct of Tlatelolco.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 平均来说，大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 是否存在正统性审查：

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

– Yes

Notes: During the Panquetzaliztli feast that was dedicated to Huitzilopochtli among the Mexicas and to Quetzalcoatl among other Nahuatl-speaking groups, blue-painted pulque was given to the victim of human sacrifice, but also to the elders member of the community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The cult of the Feathered Serpent was practiced in several types of society: chiefdoms, city-states (as in the Maya region), empires (like the Excan Tlatohloyan in Mexico Valley).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

– Yes

Notes: The Mexica calmecac was an elite training for young noble men and women. Its tutelar god was

Quetzalcoatl.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体提供基础交通设施吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

基础交通设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的体制化的军事力量吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的体制化的军事力量吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

这种独特的书面语的使用仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

请描述食物生产的形式/层级 [多选]：

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Valley of Mexico

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Feathered Serpent's cult, Nichols, Deborah L., and Enrique Rodríguez-Alegría. The Oxford Handbook of the Aztecs. New York: Oxford University Press, 2016. <https://academic.oup.com/edited->

volume/34663?login=false%20Aztec.

Reference: Feathered Serpent's cult, López Austin, Alfredo, and Leonardo López Luján. *El Pasado Indígena De México*. Ciudad de México: Fondo de Cultura Económica, 1996.

Reference: Feathered Serpent's cult, Smith, Michael E.. *The Aztecs*. John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=WaEyJ9zWZDgC>.